

1 **Ahr controls IDO1 to enforce local tolerance.**

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8 Deletion of AHR in human cells resulted in near complete loss of IDO1. The data support the existence of
9 a mechanism by which local toleragenic force is generated involving IDO1-related metabolite(s), regulated
10 through AHR control of IDO1. A systems biologic approach revealed putative function of KYNU and
11 immunoregulatory metabolite kynurenine downstream of AHR and IDO1.

12 Citations

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